

[Jack Bistricher](#), a businessman with huge experience in the real estate development sector shares the key characteristics of a successful real estate developer.

1. Risk tolerance

Bistricher indicates that some investment seekers have a hard time taking dangers. Reliable developers will do calculations and measure all contingencies associated with investing and constantly look for ways

2. Problem solving skills

Bistricher shares that they strive to find solutions to conflicts, plan sites, and deal with nearby owners to find ways to deliver the project on time and on budget. They are always ready for the expected and unexpected. When a problem occurs, they are quick enough to fix it on time and at low cost, and to mitigate any damage.

3. Creativity

According to [the experienced businessman](#), Bistricher, they must be creative people who have the vision to look to the future of foundation technology. New building materials, state-of-the-art construction methods, and exciting designs are what a successful developer should consider.

4. Interpersonal skills

Bistricher specifies that they have the skills to communicate with people with ease. They can quickly build a genuine relationship and bond with people from all walks of life. They deal with a wide variety of people as buyers, consultants and local council members and more. They have the leadership skills to get the most out of their relationships.

5. Ability to detect potential

As Jack Bistricher, [the COO of Talisker Corporation](#) explains, in real estate investing, great opportunities are few, and when they do appear, they definitely don't last forever. A successful real estate developer has the ability to discover a good opportunity and to determine its chances.

The real estate market is very unpredictable, therefore, to be successful as a developer it is very important to always keep up with the latest trends in the real estate sector.

Do not think that a real estate developer is only the one who directs the orchestra and only delegates responsibilities, we needed a very important part: MONEY.